

Crime Against Women in India – An Analysis

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Abstract

Crime against women has been a major challenge to the whole world. The society has witnessed a huge rise in violence against women. Though governments are trying to bring in stricter laws to punish the perpetrators, the crime rates have not seen a dip. On the contrary crime against women has been increasing and it has almost doubled over the past ten years. The present paper is an attempt to analyze the different types of crimes committed against women in Tamil Nadu and India in order to find possible causes and solutions to the problem. A comparison of the total crime rates within the districts in Tamil Nadu and a state wise comparison of total crime committed throughout India are presented. A trend analysis is done with the past ten years crime data. The paper tries to throw light on the possible reasons for committing the crimes and what steps could be taken to control them. The study is supported with adequate literature review throughout.

Keywords: Crime against women, domestic violence, crime rate, Tamil Nadu, India

Introduction

Crime against women has seen a phenomenal increase in the past few years. Naidu and Nayak (2007) blame it on the declining values in the society, while Mukherjee, Rustagi and Krishnaji (2001) find criminalisation of politics to be another major reason as many criminals are entering into politics. The film industry could also be a culprit, for glorifying crimes against women (Dasgupta 1996).

Though the Indian government is trying hard to tackle this social menace by bringing in more police vigil and stringent laws, something seems to be lacking. In a male dominated society like India women are struggling to live a life with dignity. Women are faced with threat both within and outside their homes. Crimes against women like domestic violence, rape, murder, kidnapping, assault to modesty, human trafficking, dowry and suicides are rampant.

Many studies conducted in India prove that crime against women is grossly underreported. (Jain, Mathur, Kothari and Mathur 2008, Mukhopadhyay, Partha, Karmakar, Sarkar, Chatterjee and Nigam 2010, Al-Azad, Raman, Ahmad, Wahab and Ali 2011). Women do not report crimes due to various reasons like the fear of society, the treatment they get in police stations, fear of not getting fair treatment

and justice, pressure from family and relatives, humiliation etc. If these alarming figures are actually an underrepresentation of the actual scenario, it's time for every citizen of India to unite and stand as one against exploitation and crime against women.

Literature Review

The National Family Health Survey (NFHS)-3 conducted a survey on gender equality and women's empowerment in India. It was shocking to see that 54% of women in the age group of 15-49 agreed on one or more reasons on a man's 'right' to beat his wife. Whereas 51% of men said it was ok to beat ones wife (Kishor and Gupta 2009).

Kanekar and Seksaria 2003 argued that the way a woman dresses or behaves has nothing to do with crimes rates. They emphasised that the attitude a boy or a man carries against a women determined the crime rates better.

Scully and Marol (1985) interviewed 114 convicted rapists. They found out that many rapists used rape as revenge or punishment. A few liked the power of accessing otherwise unavailable women, a few had simply coupled it with burglary, and a few described it as an exciting adventure which gave them power over the victims.

Fimate and devi (1998) found out in a study that in most cases the victims of rape were already known to the rapist.

Madan in the year 2014 found out that females were not considered as equals to their male counterparts, in spite of increase in women employment and education.

S C Sarkar et.al conducted a research on 90 rape victims and found that 41% of them were raped in their own house by a known person.

Objectives of the Study

The objective of the present study is to

- Analyze the crimes which are committed against women in Tamil Nadu and India.
- Study possible reasons which lead to committing crimes against women

Methodology

The present study uses secondary data from the National Crime Records Bureau (NCRB), Ministry of Home Affairs. An analysis on crime against women in Tamil Nadu and India is done based on the report released by the National Crime Records Bureau, Ministry of Home Affairs for the year 2015. The previous ten years data is used to do a trend analysis.

Analysis and Discussion

Table 1: Incidence of crime against women

Crime by Type	Tamil Nadu		India	
	Crime count	Rank	Crime count	Rank
Cruelty by Husband or his Relatives	1900	1	113401	1
Kidnapping & Abduction	1335	2	59277	3
Assault on Women with intent to outrage her Modesty	1163	3	82416	2
Immoral Traffic Prevention Act	491	4	2424	10
Rape	421	5	34651	4
Dowry Prohibition Act, 1961	333	6	9894	5
Abetment of Suicides of Women	79	7	4060	9
Dowry Deaths	65	8	7634	7
Attempt to commit Rape	29	9	4437	8
Insult to the Modesty of Women	20	10	8684	6
Indecent Representation of Women (P) Act, 1986				
Protection of Women from Domestic Violence Act, 2005	7	11	40	12
Importation of Girls from Foreign Country	4	12	461	11
Protection of Children from Sexual Offences Act	0	13	6	13
	0	14	0	14

Source: National Crime Records Bureau Report (2015), Ministry of Home Affairs

In Table 1 the different types of crimes are listed with the number of crimes committed and the position they hold with respect to Tamil Nadu and India. Cruelty by husband or his relatives ranks first in Tamil Nadu. Kidnapping & abduction, assault on women with intent to outrage her modesty rank second and third respectively. Immoral Traffic prevention ranks fourth and rape ranks fifth. Considering India as a whole, domestic violence ranks first. It is followed by assault on women with intent to outrage her modesty and kidnapping & abduction. Rape stands fourth and crimes related to dowry are on the fifth position. Domestic violence alone accounts for a whopping 34.6% of the total crimes committed against women in India.

Figure 2 – Crime against women in Tamil Nadu – District wise

Figure 2 represents a district wise breakup of crimes committed against women in the year 2015. Madurai ranks first with 753 crimes (these are the crimes registered under Madurai and Madurai city put together). Chennai ranks second in the crime list with 523 registered cases. Villupuram, Dindigal and Thirunelveli are in the third fourth and fifth places with 373, 338 and 326 crimes committed against women respectively. Salem is in the sixth place followed by Sivagangai, Coimbatore, Cuddalore, Virudhunagar, Trichy, Vellore, Dharmapuri, Thoothukudi, Krishnagiri, Kanyakumari, Theni, Ramanathapuram, Thiruvannamalai, Thanjavur, Tiruppur, Nagapattinam, Namakkal, Thiruvarur, Erode, Pudukottai and Karur. The districts with least crimes are Kanchipuram, Perambalur, Nilgiris, Thiruvallur and Ariyalur with 56, 51, 46, 34 and 33 crimes respectively.

Source: National Crime Records Bureau Report (2015), Ministry of Home Affairs

Figure 3 – Crime against women in India state wise

Figure 3 represents a state wise breakup of the crimes committed against women throughout India in the year 2015 according to the National Crime Records Bureau Report, Ministry of Home Affairs. Uttar Pradesh tops the chart with 35527 cases followed by West Bengal with 33218 cases and Maharashtra with 31126 cases. Rajasthan stands in the fourth place followed by Madhya Pradesh, Assam, Odisha, Delhi UT, Andhra Pradesh, Telangana, Bihar, Karnataka, Kerala, Haryana, Gujarat, Jharkhand, Tamil Nadu, Chhattisgarh, Punjab, Jammu & Kashmir and the rest of the districts. Tamil Nadu holds the 17th position on the list of crimes against women in India.

Source: National Crime Records Bureau Report (2015), Ministry of Home Affairs

Figure 4: Crime trend in India – An analysis of the past ten years

Source: National Crime Records Bureau Report (2006-2015), Ministry of Home Affairs

The above graph shows the crime trend against women for the past ten years in India (from 2006 to 2015). The highest increase in crime rate of 27% is seen from the year 2012 to 2013, followed by a 12% increase from the year 2006 to 2007 and a 7% increase in the years 2010 to 2011 and 2011 to 2012. A decrease in crime of -3% is seen from the year 2014 to 2015. The crime rates have almost doubled from 164765 to 327394 in the last ten years.

Causes for Crimes Against Women

Individual Determinants

High levels of testosterone and low levels of serotonin are found to be indicators of aggression.

A number of studies have been done on Psychopathology and personality traits and it was found that a high incidence of personality disorders like antisocial personality, borderline personality disorder and post traumatic stress syndrome were found among men who abused their wives. (Hamberger and Hastings, 1986, 1988, 1989, Dutton and Starzomski 1993, 1994)

Alcoholics are more prone to violent behaviours. In many cases of domestic abuse it is reported that the husband was in an inebriated state. Sex and power motives are a major driving force when it comes to violence against women. Attaining an unavailable women and assaulting her gives the perpetrator a sense of power.

Societal Determinants

A parental preference for sons is culturally ingrained which is originating from their importance as caregivers is leading to poorer consequences for daughters.

A secure and peaceful home environment is a prerequisite for healthy personality development. It is seen that boys who had poor parental care and supervision, suffered from parental neglect grow up to be abusers of their spouse and family later on. Men raised in families which emphasise on the superiority of males and encourage gender bias seem to have problems in accepting their partners as equals. Societies which encourage male dominance also produce more offenders in the future.

Combating Crime Against Women

The best way to stop violence is to prevent it from happening. A focus on prevention of violence would be a better bet compared to bringing in laws to punish the violators. Educating a girl child is most important as this brings in autonomy. Young girls and women should be taught to be more

assertive, to take strong decisions, to learn to say no in a relationship, to feel strong and to feel bold. Teaching them at least one self defence technique would come in handy at times of crisis.

Educating young boys and girls on gender equality and to mutually respect each other in a relationship would be the starting point in ending violence against women. The United Nations 57th session of the commission on the status of women placed a strong emphasis on gender equality and empowerment of women.

Conclusion

Violence against women has devastating consequences. The physical consequences include injury, bruises, cuts, burns, broken bones, pain, contracting sexually transmitted diseases, unwanted pregnancy, miscarriages and in extreme cases death. Psychological consequences include confusion, shock, disbelief, denial, withdrawal symptoms, post traumatic stress disorders, depression, anxiety, suicidal ideation, guilt, shame, low self esteem, self blame, worthlessness, generalised anxiety, obsessive compulsive disorder, drug dependence, drug abuse, alcoholism and many more. The upward trend in crimes against women emphasizes the urgency and need to prevent them. While policy indicatives in addition to progressive laws and their effective enforcement do help in combating the crimes, the best way to stop violence is to prevent it from happening. Education is an essential means of empowering women with necessary wisdom, skills and self confidence to face difficult situations in the private and public spheres. Educating children from an early age on the importance of gender equality could bring an attitudinal shift for women to be considered as equal within their homes and in the broader society. Empowering women and promoting gender equality is not only helping in preventing the crimes against women, it also helps in accelerating sustainable development referred in the United nations Development Program's sustainable development goals (United Nations The sustainable development goals report 2018).

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